

Established Facts in the paper *Isolation and characterization of a bat SARS-like coronavirus that uses the ACE2 receptor*

(Picture source: CNN)

1. [*Isolation and characterization of a bat SARS-like coronavirus that uses the ACE2 receptor*](#) was published by Nature on 28 November 2013.
2. The information about the authors is listed below.

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LETTER

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Isolation and characterization of a bat SARS-like coronavirus that uses the ACE2 receptor

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(Picture source:nature)

3. Source of Fund:

No.	Name of Fund	Official Chinese Name of the Fund if from China	Specific Number of Grant
1	State Key Program for Basic Research	国家重点基础研究发展计划 (973 计划)	2011CB504701 and 2010CB530100
2	National Natural Science Foundation of China	国家自然科学基金委员会	81290341 and 31321001
3	Scientific and technological basis special project	科技基础性工作专项	2013FY113500
4	CSIRO OCE Science Leaders Award, National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases		R01AI079231
5	National Institutes of Health (NIH)/National Science Foundation 'Ecology and Evolution of Infectious Diseases' award from the NIH Fogarty International Center		R01TW005869
6	NIH Fogarty International Center supported by International Influenza Funds from the Office of the Secretary of the Department of Health and Human Services		R56TW009502
7	United States Agency for International Development Emerging		

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	Pandemic Threats PREDICT		

(Picture source:nature)

Introduction:

State Key Program for Basic Research and Scientific and technological basis special project of China are part of 12th Five Year Special Plan for Developing National Basic Research of China published in February 2012 (The Plan). According to the plan,

State Key Program for Basic Research included research on pathogenic biology of important infectious diseases, epidemiological characteristics, infection and pathogenesis of infectious diseases,; *Scientific and technological basis special project* included special scientific observations and investigations on the epidemiology of important genetic diseases and, international cooperation and exchange, and;

State Key Lab is used in Military-Civil Fusion technology program.State Key Labs also exist in Hong Kong and Macau.

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According to the Constitution of National Natural Science Foundation of China, The Ministry of Science and Technology of PRC is responsible for the management of the National Natural Science Foundation of China, and conducts macro-management, overall coordination, supervision and evaluation of the work of the National Natural Science Foundation. The National Natural Science Foundation of China administers the National Natural Science Foundation. The Chinese Communist Party Cell of the National Natural Science Foundation of China is a leading organization established by the Central Committee of Chinese Communist Party and plays a leading role in the development of the National Natural Science Foundation of China, leading all departments and all staff to implement CCP's line, policy and decision deployment.

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国家基础研究发展“十二五”专项规划

中华人民共和国科学技术部

国家自然科学基金委员会

2012年2月

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5. 健康科学领域

围绕提高疾病的防治水平等重大需求，力争在生命活动的生理与病理过程、疾病的发生发展机理及其防治的基础理论等方面取得突破；加强重要传染性疾病和中医理论基础研究；关注转化医学，预期在疾病早期预警、早期预防、早期治疗的新技术新方法和个体化治疗等方面取得显著进展，为提高人民健康水平提供有力的科技支撑。

主要研究方向：非传染性慢性复杂疾病、衰老和衰老相关疾病以及常见多发疾病的致病机理；计划生育与生殖健康的基础研究；灾害医学及环境对健康影响；重大疾病相关药物研发的新思路、新靶点研究；生物医学新方法、新技术、新概念的相关基础研究。

重要传染病基础研究：重点研究重要传染性疾病的病原生物学，传染病流行特征、感染和发病机制、诊断治疗及疫苗和药物研发的科学问题；发展传染病监测、预警、预防、诊断和治疗的新策略。

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一是加强对重点地区的科学考察调查，组织青藏高原、南方丘陵山区、欧亚草原、东北亚森林、长三角、珠三角、环渤海以及西部干旱地区等典型地区的综合科学考察，对资料空缺匮乏区域、本底资料

急需更新的区域实施补充考察调查；二是加强农业、生物、海洋、冰川、地质地理、古生物、人体生理常数、重要遗传性疾病流行病学、心理健康等重要领域的专项科学考察与调查，三是加强国际合作与交流，联合周边国家开展跨境典型区域的科学考察调查。

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（五）基础研究创新基地

1. 国家（重点）实验室体系

国家重点实验室是我国开展高水平基础研究、聚集和培养优秀科技人才、开展高层次科技交流合作的重要基地。经过 20 多年的发展，已形成较为完善的实验室体系，目前包括六大类别：国家实验室、依托高校和科研院所建设的国家重点实验室、依托企业建设的国家重点实验室、依托军队院校和科研院所建设的军民共建国家重点实验室、依托港澳地区高校和科研院所建设的国家重点实验室伙伴实验室、省部共建国家重点实验室培育基地。“十二五”期间，国家（重点）实验室体系将在“开放、流动、联合、竞争”运行机制和“共建共享”思路指导下，继续加强顶层设计和布局，规范和完善管理措施，进一步发挥其在科技创新中的骨干和引领作用。

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根据国家重大战略需求，结合国家技术创新工程的实施，依托企业新建一批国家重点实验室，加强在战略性新兴产业的布局。规范管理，积极探索适应企业特点的支持方式、管理模式和运行机制。充分发挥国家重点实验室在产业技术创新战略联盟中的关键作用，促进产学研合作，提高我国产业的自主创新能力和国际竞争力。

根据“军民结合、寓军于民”国防科技创新体系的建设需要，依托军队高校和科研院所新建若干国家重点实验室。围绕军民共用的重大科学技术问题开展基础研究和应用研究，加强合作交流和资源共享，促进军民科技融合，形成全国优秀科技力量服务国防科技创新、国防科技成果迅速向民用转化的良好格局。

稳步推进港澳地区国家重点实验室伙伴实验室的建设工作，促进其与内地科研单位的交流与合作，共同提高科研水平。规范管理，探索相关管理机制和政策措施。

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国家自然科学基金委员会章程

(2005年3月17日国家自然科学基金委员会第五届二次全体委员会议通过；
2008年5月28日国家自然科学基金委员会第六届一次全体委员会议修订；
2017年3月28日国家自然科学基金委员会第七届五次全体委员会议修订
2019年3月26日国家自然科学基金委员会第八届二次全体委员会议修订)

第一章 总则

第一条 为了确立国家自然科学基金委员会工作规范和行为准则，保障国家自然科学基金事业健康发展，以习近平新时代中国特色社会主义思想为指导，根据《中华人民共和国科学技术进步法》和《国家自然科学基金条例》制定本章程。

国家自然科学基金委员会章程

(2005年3月17日国家自然科学基金委员会第五届二次全体委员会议通过；
2008年5月28日国家自然科学基金委员会第六届一次全体委员会议修订；
2017年3月28日国家自然科学基金委员会第七届五次全体委员会议修订
2019年3月26日国家自然科学基金委员会第八届二次全体委员会议修订)

第一章 总则

第一条 为了确立国家自然科学基金委员会工作规范和行为准则，保障国家自然科学基金事业健康发展，以习近平新时代中国特色社会主义思想为指导，根据《中华人民共和国科学技术进步法》和《国家自然科学基金条例》制定本章程。

第二条 科学技术部负责管理国家自然科学基金委员会，依法对国家自然科学基金工作进行宏观管理、统筹协调和监督评估。国家自然科学基金委员会依法管理国家自然科学基金，相对独立运行，负责资助计划、项目设置和评审、立项、监督等组织实施工作。

第三条 国家自然科学基金委员会坚持中国共产党的领导，增强“四个意识”，坚定“四个自信”，做到“两个维护”，深入贯彻落实党中央、国务院关于加快实施创新驱动发展战略的重大决策部署，有效运用国家自然科学基金，支持基础研究和应用基础研究，坚持自由探索，加强战略前瞻部署，培养人才和团队，推动学科交叉融合，增强源头创新能力，实现科技创新对经济社会发展的支撑和引领，促进创新型国家和世界科技强国建设。

国家自然科学基金委员会参与制定国家发展基础研究的方针、政策和规划，对国家发展科学技术的重大问题提供咨询；联合有关机构开展资助活动；同其他国家或地区的政府科学技术管理部门、资助机构和学术组织建立联系并开展国际/港澳台合作；支持国内其他科学基金的工作；承办国务院及有关部门委托或交办的其他事项。

第四条 中国共产党国家自然科学基金委员会党组是党中央在国家自然科学基金委员会设立的领导机构，在国家自然科学基金事业发展中发挥领导核心作用。领导各部门和全体工作人员贯彻落实党的路线、方针、政策和决策部署，加强党的建设，落实全面从严治党主体责任。

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(Picture source: gov.cn)

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4. SARS-CoV is severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus.
5. SL-CoVs is SARS-like coronaviruses.
6. ACE2 is angiotensin converting enzyme II.
7. Bat SL-CoV-WIV1 is first recorded isolation of a live SL-CoV
8. SARS-CoV used the human ACE2 molecule as its entry receptor, and this is considered a hallmark of its cross-species transmissibility.
9. The receptor binding domain (RBD) located in the amino-terminal region of the SARS-CoV spike (S) protein is directly involved in binding to ACE2.
10. Replacing the RBD of one SL-CoV S protein with SARS-CoV S conferred the ability to use human ACE2 and replicate efficiently in mice.
11. No SL-CoVs have been isolated from bats, and no wild-type SL-CoV of bat origin has been shown to use ACE2 before the paper was issued.

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The 2002–3 pandemic of SARS¹ and the ongoing emergence of the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV)² demonstrate that CoVs are a significant public health threat. SARS-CoV was shown to use the human ACE2 molecule as its entry receptor, and this is considered a hallmark of its cross-species transmissibility¹¹. The receptor binding domain (RBD) located in the amino-terminal region (amino acids 318–510) of the SARS-CoV spike (S) protein is directly involved in binding to ACE2 (ref. 12). However, despite phylogenetic evidence that SARS-CoV evolved from bat SL-CoVs, all previously identified SL-CoVs have major sequence differences from SARS-CoV in the RBD of their S proteins, including one or two deletions^{6,9}. Replacing the RBD of one SL-CoV S protein with SARS-CoV S conferred the ability to use human ACE2 and replicate efficiently in mice^{9,13}. However, to date, no SL-CoVs have been isolated from bats, and no wild-type SL-CoV of bat origin has been shown to use ACE2.

of their S proteins, including one or two deletions^{6,9}. Replacing the RBD of one SL-CoV S protein with SARS-CoV S conferred the ability to use human ACE2 and replicate efficiently in mice^{9,13}. However, to date, no SL-CoVs have been isolated from bats, and no wild-type SL-CoV of bat origin has been shown to use ACE2.

of lineages that ultimately lead to SARS-CoV. The most notable sequence difference between SARS-CoV and previously identified SL-CoV S proteins. First, they have higher amino acid identity to SARS-CoV (85% and 96% for RsSHC014 and F104013, respectively) and there are no deletions and they have perfect conservation of the SARS-CoV RBD region (Extended I

We conducted a 12-month longitudinal survey (April 2011–September 2012) of SL-CoVs in a colony of *Rhinolophus sinicus* at a single location

¹Center for Emerging Infectious Diseases, State Key Laboratory of Virology, Wuhan Institute of Virology of the Chinese Academy of Sciences, Wuhan 430071, China 10001, USA. ²One Health Institute, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of California, Davis, California 95616, USA. ³CSIRO Australian Animal Health Laboratory, St Leonards, New South Wales 1585, Australia. ⁴College of Life Sciences, East China Normal University, Shanghai 200062, China. ⁵Emerging Infectious Diseases Program, Duke-NUS Graduate Medical School, Singapore. *These authors contributed equally to this work.

Despite the rapid accumulation of bat CoV sequences in the last decade, there has been no report of successful virus isolation^{6,22,23}. We attempted isolation from SL-CoV PCR-positive samples. Using an optimized protocol and Vero E6 cells, we obtained one isolate which caused cytopathic effect during the second blind passage. Purified virions

(Picture source: nature)

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12. The paper's authors attempted isolation from SL-CoV PCR-positive samples. Using an optimized protocol and Vero E6 cells, they obtained one isolate, named as named SL-CoV-WIV1, which caused cytopathic effect during the second blind passage.
13. To determine whether WIV1 can use ACE2 as a cellular entry receptor, they performed virus infectivity studies using HeLa cells expressing or not expressing ACE2 from humans and found that WIV1 is able to use ACE2 of different origins as an entry receptor and replicated efficiently in the ACE2-expressing cells. It's the first identification of a wild-type bat SL-CoV capable of using ACE2 as an entry receptor.
14. Rs3367, or RsSHC014, is the descendent of a recombination of lineages that ultimately lead to SARS-CoV and SL-CoV Rs672.

breakpoints were detected with strong r values ($\sim 10^{-10}$) and supported by similarity plot and bootscan analysis (Extended Data Fig. 5a, b). Breakpoints were located at nucleotides 20,827, 26,553 and 28,685 in the Rs3367 (and RsSHC014) genome, and generated recombination fragments covering nucleotides 20,827–26,533 (5,727 nucleotides) (including partial open reading frame (ORF) 1b, full-length S, ORF3, E and partial M gene) and nucleotides 26,534–28,685 (2,133 nucleotides) (including partial ORF M, full-length ORF6, ORF7, ORF8 and partial N gene). Phylogenetic analysis using the major and minor parental regions suggested that **Rs3367, or RsSHC014, is the descendent of a recombination of lineages that ultimately lead to SARS-CoV and SL-CoV Rs672** (Fig. 1b).

Figure 1 | Phylogenetic tree based on amino acid sequences of the S RBD region and the two parental regions of bat SL-CoV Rs3367 or RsSHC014.

R. ferrumequinum and *R. macrotis*, respectively, collected in 2004. Bat SARS-related CoV BM48-31 was identified from *F. Pulex* in 2008. Bat CoV HKU10-1 was identified from *B. pteropus* in 2003.

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To determine whether WIV1 can use ACE2 as a cellular entry receptor, we conducted virus infectivity studies using HeLa cells expressing or not expressing ACE2 from humans, civets or Chinese horseshoe bats. We found that WIV1 is able to use ACE2 of different origins as an entry receptor and replicated efficiently in the ACE2-expressing cells (Fig. 3). This is, to our knowledge, the first identification of a wild-type bat SL-CoV capable of using ACE2 as an entry receptor.

(Picture source: nature)

Important links regarding SARS-CoV-2:

[Exclusive Eyewitness Account: I Saw Over 1000 Bodies in Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University](#)

[THE WUHAN FILES Bombshell clues that 'PROVE' China hid Covid lab leak in 'cover up of the century worse than Watergate'](#)

[SARS-CoV-2 Transmission From People Without COVID-19 Symptoms](#)

[HUGE: Uttar Pradesh, India Announces State Is COVID-19 Free Proving the Effectiveness of "Deworming Drug" IVERMECTIN](#)

[World Bank succumbs to Chinese monopoly](#)

[Covid-19 Panel of Scientists Investigating Origins of Virus Is Disbanded](#)

[Behind Covid-19 Booster Authorization Were Disagreements on Evidence, Broad Access](#)

[Covid cover: National security and news media in China](#)

[China's People Will Tell the World the Truth About COVID-19](#)

[WHO probe's 'clear' conflicts of interest](#)

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[The MARTINZ Critical Review - Ep#88 - The missing link; the real origins of the SARSCov2 virus - with Dr Li-Meng Yan,](#)

[Wuhan Lab Wanted to Genetically Enhance Bat Viruses to Study Human Risks, Documents Show](#)

[DARPA Denies Funding Wuhan Institute of Virology Amid Alleged Document Leak](#)

[Wuhan Scientists Planned to Release Coronaviruses into Chinese Cave Bats 18 Months Prior to Outbreak](#)

[Whistleblower Confirms Lawrence Sellin's Reporting at Gateway Pundit From July – Wuhan Military Games Were China's First Intentional COVID Super-Spreader Event #BioTerrorism](#)

[I was sceptical of 'lab leak' theory. But new info, China's cover-up made me see differently](#)

[It is No Great Mystery, SARS-CoV-2 Origin is the Wuhan Lab – 3rd Yan Report](#)

[Covid-19 origins: Why the search for the source is vital](#)

[SUPER VIRUS China lab created coronavirus '10,000-times stronger than usual' as fears rage over Wuhan 'leak', scientists warn](#)

[Fauci's Smoking Gun and China's Campaign to Brainwash Americans](#)

[Stanford professors urge U.S. to end program looking for Chinese spies in academia](#)

[Organized Scientific Fraud: SARS-CoV-2 is an Unrestricted Bioweapon](#)

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